

Final design of the two prototypes and pilot at TRL 7

Deliverable 6.1

Submission Date: 30 April 2020
Lead Partner: AQUALIA
Contributor(s): AQUALIA, WETSUS

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This WP proposes a "start to end" valorisation process of the urban sewage sludge (USS) and organic fraction from municipal solid waste (OFMSW) to obtain ready-to-use products. Different processes will be studied to demonstrate the feasibility to obtain high-value products from raw biowastes (OFMSW and USS). These processes will be validated in prototypes operated in three demonstration sites: DS 1 (ES), DS6 (CZ) and DS7 (NL). Special attention will be given to the key operation parameters and system design for the production of target valuable end-products to be adapted at DSs.

The advanced anaerobic digestion pilot plant treats primary and secondary sludge (mixed sludge) produced in the Estiviel Sewage Treatment Plant (STP) located in DS1 (Spain) through a two-staged bioelectrochemical route (Dual Anaerobic Digestion). This process aims to obtain high quality biogas and biosolids with enhanced sanitation properties (pathogen reduction) for land application.

At DS7 (The Netherlands), a pilot of the PHARIO technology is being developed for PHA (Polyhydroxyalkanoates) production from municipal surplus secondary activated sludge and fermented organic waste. PHA are biodegradable thermoplastics with the potential to replace fossil fuel based polymers.

The bioelectrochemical system (BES) target is to bioelectrochemically convert the CO₂ content of the biogas produced from the digestion of USS or OFMSW into valuable organic compounds. This prototype has been installed in DS 1 (Spain) treating biogas from OFMSW and will be further tested in DS 6 (Czech Republic) in future stages of the project, treating biogas from USS.

Deliverable 6.1 aims to describe the final design of these two prototypes and the pilot plant that will be the tools to demonstrate the feasibility to obtain high value products. These two prototypes and pilot use different streams and down-streams produced during USS and OFMSW treatment.

For more information, contact:

Project Coordinator: César Aliaga, caliaga@itene.com

Project Communications: James Ling, j.ling@greenovate-europe.eu

Deliverable contact: Leticia Pereira, leticia.pereira@fcc.es; Erik de Vries, Erik.deVries@wetsus.nl

